

Note on the Constitution of Formic Acid and Formates.

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Much speculation has centered round the question of the constitution of formic acid and its salt (Ray, *Nature*, 1934, **133**, 646; and Sarkar and Ray, *Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1935, p. 109). These investigators advance the view that the acid molecule has the structure $\text{H} \leftarrow \text{C} = \text{O}$, while the ion the structure

$:\text{C} = \text{O}$ on the grounds of the large difference in properties of the

$$\begin{array}{c} \uparrow \\ \text{OH} \end{array}$$

non-ionised acid and the acid residue. It is pointed out that this structure brings to the fore-ground the particular reducing character of the formate ion, which has a lone pair of electrons, in contrast to the acid molecule or its esters. Thus it is the hydrogen attached to the carbon atom that ionises, but not the one in the hydroxyl group, which once again distinguishes formic acid from its higher analogues, *i.e.*, acetic or butyric acids. In further support of this view it is shown that cadmium formate does not give rise to the Raman line 2930,* corresponding to the C-H linkage and present in formic acid, and that the metallic formates and nitrites exhibit isomorphic relations, especially in their barium and strontium compounds.

Seshadri (*Current Science*, 1934, **3**, 353) disagrees with this view and postulates in its place a labile structure) to the acid molecule,

with the heterodox hypothesis of Ray and Sarkar and yet explain the absence of the well known Raman line.

* It is interesting to note also that Ghosh and Kar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, **35**, 1735) studied the Raman-spectra of sodium formate solution and noticed the absence of the Raman-shift $\Delta\nu = 2930$ whereas in solution of sodium acetate, this Raman-shift was easily detected.

The work of Sheibler on compounds like $C(OC_2H_5)_2$ and $C(ONa)(OC_2H_5)$ is cited in support of the dihydroxymethylene structure. While it is true that the lone pair of electrons belonging to the C-atom may endow it with special reducing properties, one is inclined to ask the very pertinent question how this structure with two equivalent hydrogen atoms can satisfy the avowedly monobasic character of the acid. The labile structure is more in the nature of a zealous endeavour to save the classical formulæ of organic chemistry from the ruthless onslaughts of the modern physical chemist with his earthing X-ray and spectroscopic analysis. It is probably once again this fervour which actuated the statement, "If this could be proved, (the ionisation of the hydrogen atom in the C-H linkage) formic acid would become not only exceptional among the fatty acids, but would hold a unique position among all organic compounds,' in the face of unequivocal evidence from Raman spectra and isomorphism of formates and nitrites.

Further evidence for the new type of formic acid molecule may be advanced on considerations of the parachor. Adopting the improved Mumford and Philips values for the various atoms and the singlet, doublet and semi-polar bonds, the parachor for the

structure $\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \leftarrow \text{C} = \text{O} \\ \uparrow \\ \text{OH} \end{array}$ works to 93.6 units while that for the structure $\begin{array}{c} \text{OH} \\ \diagup \\ \text{C} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{OH} \end{array}$ to 78.7 units. The former value is so much

in agreement with that calculated from data on surface tension, *i.e.*, 93.9 units that one is tempted on this ground alone to adopt the new structure.